

A. Reviewer's Report

The article titled "*Teachers' Challenges and the Implementation of Universal Primary Education in Hoima District: A Case Study of Primary Schools in Hoima City*" delves into the significance of Social Network Analysis (SNA) as a methodological tool in social sciences. The abstract emphasizes the shift from solely quantitative approaches to incorporating qualitative methods to address a broader spectrum of social issues. It highlights the importance of understanding connections between social subjects, institutions, or organizations. The keywords "Social Network" and "Qualitative Research Methodology" encapsulate the core themes explored in the paper.

In the introduction, the author delineates the relevance of SNA in contemporary research areas such as Diversity Management, Social Capital, and Trust Crisis. The historical evolution of social network concepts is traced back 50 years, emphasizing its interdisciplinary nature and role in understanding social structures. The discussion elucidates the dynamic nature of social networks, presenting them as intricate structures with evolving properties. The article advocates for a qualitative approach to SNA to delve deeper into social phenomena, challenging the dominance of mathematical formalization in the field.

The author discusses three approaches to social network analysis: whole networks, ego nets, and two-mode networks. Each approach is delineated with its respective data collection methods and analytical implications. Whole network analysis is advocated for capturing intricate connections and indirect ties, although acknowledged as methodologically challenging. Ego nets and two-mode networks are presented as alternative approaches with their own strengths and limitations.

Comparing qualitative and quantitative approaches, the article posits the qualitative method as more suitable for sensitive or complex research topics. It underscores the limitations of closed-ended questions in capturing nuanced perspectives, advocating for a more flexible and exploratory approach to data collection and analysis. The qualitative approach is seen as particularly beneficial in situations where previous research fails to adequately define the phenomenon under investigation.

The conclusion reiterates the interconnected nature of social phenomena and the importance of choosing appropriate methodologies to explore these connections. It emphasizes the qualitative approach as a means to gain a deeper understanding of social networks, allowing researchers to delve into micro-level perspectives and identify nuances within social phenomena. The article concludes by affirming the establishment of the Sociology of Social Networks field and its potential for further exploration and analysis of various social issues.

The author's perspective aligns with a growing trend in social sciences towards integrating qualitative methods into network analysis. While traditional approaches have predominantly focused on quantitative methods, there is an increasing recognition of the need for qualitative approaches to capture the complexities of social interactions. This perspective resonates with previous research that advocates for a more holistic understanding of social networks (Borgatti, 2009; Crossley et al., 2015).

Overall, the article provides valuable insights into the methodological considerations of qualitative network research. By highlighting the importance of understanding social networks beyond mathematical formalization, the author contributes to a broader discourse on the role of qualitative methods in advancing social science research.

A. Significance of the topics/issues to the field of research		
Extremely significant	10	X
Important	8	
Modest	6	
Trivial	4	
Unimportant	2	
B. Value of writing and other elements (figures, tables, graphical elements)		
Superior	10	X
Good	8	
Minor problems	6	
Major problems	4	
Completely inadequate	2	
C. Conceptual consistency (clarity of objectives, treatment of relevant literature, consistency of reasoning, argumentation)		
Superior	10	X
Good	8	
Minor problems	6	
Major problems	4	
Completely inadequate	2	
D. Methodological consistency (research design, sampling, data collection/analyses as relevant to qualitative/quantitative data)		
Superior	10	X
Good	8	
Minor problems	6	
Major problems	4	
Completely inadequate	2	
E. General discussion and conclusions (implications, limitations, future research, recommendations)		
Superior	10	X
Good	8	
Minor problems	6	
Major problems	4	
Completely inadequate	2	
F. Paper's contribution to the research field		
Extremely significant	10	X
Important	8	
Modest	6	
Trivial	4	
Unimportant	2	
Recommendations		
Accept unconditionally, without the necessity of major content and structure adjustments	(55-60)	X
Accept conditionally, subject to minor revision, according to the accompanying comments	(50-54)	
Encourage revision, according to the accompanying comments	(40-49)	
Reject in current form, but allow resubmission of a substantially different version, according to the accompanying comments	(25-39)	
Reject unconditionally, because the likelihood of a successful revision is remote	(<24)	

B. Conclusion

The research work has a good value of conceptual consistency and a very good coverage of the planned topic, a good research design, and clarity of the objectives.

The article is **ACCEPTED** for publication unconditionally, without the necessity of major content and structure adjustments.

C. Remarks

a. Article's formatting

Some minor aesthetic adjustments (formatting) will be performed during the editing phase:

- formatting of the title: (font size, font type, font case, position, spacing, and indentation);
- formatting of authors' name and affiliation (editing, font type, font size, font case, position);
- header/footer editing (adding authors' names and article's title, editing page number, and adding correspondence email address). Previously added footers/endnotes will be preserved and (or) actualized;
- adding the reserved DOI; abstract, keywords content formatting: (font size, font type, font case, position, spacing and indentation, paragraphs editing);
- tables, figures, images, diagrams formatting (size, border, font size, font type, font case, position);
- in-text citation and reference list formatting (font size, font type, font case, position, style, spacing and indentation, hyperlinks editing and verification).

The content editing will be done by the editors.

b. Content adjustments

The content of the submitted manuscript will be changed only after the editing phase and after being communicated as a recommended content update to the authors. The recommended content adjustments are meant to be made by the author; if, for various reasons, the authors consider the editor intervention more appropriate, these adjustments can be made by the editors in the editing phase.

c. Edited article adjustments/updates

Before the publication, the article is sent back to the authors, in an editable for (Word DOCX file format). Last content updates, minor corrections can be made by the author(s) in this phase, without affecting the document structure and formatting. We highly recommend the author's contribution to this last phase; by that, the resulting document has the authors' final agreement on the article's form and content.

The following sections/elements need to be included in the article (updated, if necessary):

- authors(s) affiliation as: position, department, institution, country. If necessary, more affiliations can be included.
- a correspondence email address. If necessary, more email addresses can be included.
- a Conflict of Interest statement
- an About the Author(s) section containing: author(s) academic, position, education, participation, achievements, links to academic institutional webpages, and/or academic networks (Academia.edu, ResearchGate, ORCID, etc.)

Note: For non-English articles, the inclusion of a translated title, abstract, and keywords is recommended (for indexing purposes).

The following sections are required only if the authors decide on their inclusion:

- funding statements;
- ethic statements, acknowledgments;
- authors' participation in the elaboration of the research;

- study limitations, acknowledgments, etc.

d. Publication of the article

When having the final form, the article is published in the current issue (there is no waiting time for the publication of a new issue). The publication of the article is communicated to the authors via email; the email includes the following:

- a copy of the published article (as a PDF file) identical with the one published in the journal;
- a certificate of publication (as a PDF file);
- the DOI of the published article;
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